

Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews

Long, N. H., Huong, L. T., & Dung, N. H. (2023). Influence of Green Marketing Mix on Purchase Intention of Vietnamese Consumers for Green Food. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 6(3), 34-45.

ISSN 2775-9237

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1992.06.03.518

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Influence of Green Marketing Mix on Purchase Intention of Vietnamese Consumers for Green Food

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Abstract

Businesses are making efforts to implement green marketing to meet the needs of consumers and build a sustainable living environment. Many studies around the world have investigated the influence of marketing mix on green purchase behavior. In order to understand the impact of 7Ps tools of retail service marketing on Vietnamese consumers' green food purchase intention, this study surveyed 368 consumers and analyzed quantitative data. Research shows that 7Ps of green retail stores affect customers attitude and their attitude have impact on their purchase intention. This result is the basis for green food retailers in Vietnam to understand consumers and make more effective green marketing decisions.

Keywords: Marketing Mix, Purchase Intention, Green Food, Consumers

1. Introduction

Green marketing is an inevitable trend of businesses today to have a sustainable development environment. In Vietnam, many businesses have been turning to green marketing, including retail businesses. However, buying green products is still an unpopular activity among Vietnamese consumers. In order to promote green consumption intentions, Vietnamese businesses are promoting green marketing mix activities. This study was conducted to understand the relationship between the implementation of green marketing tools and green purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers. The research is conducted based on the combination of Ajzen and Fishbein's model of purchase intention (1991) with the model of marketing mix tools in the service industry (7Ps) of businesses.

2. Literature review

2.1. Theoretical foundation of the research

The theory of planned behavior was proposed by Icek Ajzen in 1991. Theories of reasoned action have been based on different theories of attitudes such as learning, value, and unification theory (e.g Heider's theory of equilibrium, Osgood and Tannenbaum's theory of conformity, and Festinger's theory of dissonance) along with distributive

theory. According to the theory of reasoned action, if people rate the suggested behavior as positive (attitude), and if they think their significant other wants them to perform the behavior (subjective norm), this leads to a higher purpose (intention) and they are more likely to do so. The high correlation of attitudes and subjective norms with behavioral intention, and subsequent behavior, has been confirmed in many studies.

There are many objections to the close relationship between behavioral intention and the actual behavior that has been proposed. Several studies show that, because of indirect limitations, behavioral intentions do not always lead to actual behavior. In particular, since behavioral intention cannot be a determinant of behavior when an individual's control over the behavior is inadequate, Ajzen introduces the theory of planned behavior by adding a new section, "behavior control". In this way, he extended the theory of rational action to the theory of planned behavior.

These two theories have been widely used by scholars in predicting the intention of performance behavior and human behavior. In marketing, these theories are used to study consumer behavior. It allows researchers to delve into the factors that directly influence buying behavior. Studies on green buying behavior are also often predicted by these two models (Sharma 2021). In this study, Sharma also confirmed that TRA and TPB models need to be considered in different cultures to confirm its applicability. Particularly for studies on green consumption behavior, TPB has proven to be a good model for research (Sharma 2021). In the study of green consumption behavior, psychological theories such as TPB are particularly relevant. However, the explanation level of TPB with green consumption behavior is not stable so we want to use this model in the context of studying the influence of green marketing mix on purchase intention of Vietnamese consumers.

Due to the nature of the topic, many behavioral theories can also be applied in research to understand the complexities of green consumer behavior. However, these behaviors are unstable. To understand more about unstable behavior, the *Attitude* variable is included in the model as an intermediate variable. Psychological theories such as TRA, TPB with the intermediate variable *Attitude* have been widely used to understand the change in consumer behavior, but they still do not completely elucidate the theory of behavior of unstable consumption. Therefore, scholars suggest that new theories or frameworks need to be developed to understand the volatile behavior of consumers compared to the gap between attitudes and actual purchase intentions.

2.2. Concepts

Kotler and Keller (2009) define a marketing mix of tools that businesses use to satisfy market demand for a number of goods or services over a given period of time and in a particular market. According to Agic et al., (2016), marketing strategy involves creating a mix of marketing tools that enable the business to achieve its goals in the target market. As consumer behavior changed, the marketing mix was not only concerned with the 4Ps, but also evolved into the 7Ps (Harrington et al., 2017) for service industries. In the context of research on retail services of Vietnamese supermarkets, the author uses the 7P model. These tools include:

A product is an item that is built or manufactured to satisfy the needs of a certain group of people. The product in 7Ps marketing can be intangible or tangible as it can be in the form of a service or a good. This is factor is ranked first because it directly determines the choice of customers. No one will choose a product that they do not need or do not meet a need.

However, units need to find out what customers want about the product. Then perfect and improve product quality to best meet these requirements and increase revenue. Make sure that the product you design and manufacture meet the needs and trends of the market you are targeting. (Kukanja et al., 2016).

Price – The price of a product is essentially the amount a customer has to pay to own it (Kotler and Keller, 2009). To be able to compete effectively with competitors and increase revenue for the unit, appropriate pricing is extremely important. It is the only factor that generates revenue for the business, sometimes you don't need to set low prices to attract customers but need to balance to make a profit for the business and be able to compete with other competitors. It can be based on market price segments, production costs to set prices for products and services. Pricing in the 7Ps marketing model is also an important component of the marketing strategy because it determines

the profitability and survival of the business. Adjusting product selling prices will have a great impact on the entire marketing strategy. At the same time, it also greatly affects the sales and demand of the product (Tjiptono and Chandra, 2005).

Place: An equally important element in the 7Ps Model is the place to display, introduce and exchange products. Products need to be available at the right distribution to bring in the best revenue. Businesses must display and distribute products in a place that is easily accessible to potential targets. This often requires a deep understanding of the market (Kushwaha and Agrawal, 2015) explaining that the actual distribution decision considers how the order is handled, where it is stored, how much stock is available, and freight way.

Promotion is a very important component of marketing as it can increase brand awareness and sales. So that customers can know the products and services provided by the business. Enterprises need to carry out promotion through communication channels, branding, promotion strategies, etc. All messages must be consistent, creating attraction for customers to choose products of the business (Marques et al., 2014).

People - includes people directly involved in serving customers of the business. A business should ensure the best "Customer Care". The attitude of everyone in the business will directly determine customer satisfaction. This is the factor that directly affects the brand of the business in terms of products and services provided. Therefore, all employees need to be professionally trained to bring the best experience to customers. For the human factor (people), the company's employees are very important in marketing. They are service providers. (Kukanja et al., 2016). Service quality will largely depend on the staff directly serving customers.

Process – Process in marketing 7P is one of the important elements of marketing. Organizational systems and processes that affect service implementation.

Quick working process, quick time and right to the agreement are always appreciated. The service experience, the waiting process to buy the product, the help of the staff and the consulting attitude. All of these will affect customer satisfaction about the business (Kushwaha and Agrawal, 2015). Process elements include purchasing facilities, and seller's quick response to consumer needs, responsiveness to consumer complaints about products and services. service (Yarimoglu, 2014).

Physical evidence – The infrastructure in the 7P model is the interaction of customers with businesses about the products and services they experience. Enterprises need to always ensure that this process is most synchronized and under strict management. Because the specificity of this service industry group is abstraction, businesses need "tangible" evidence so that customers can easily imagine the service provided (Khan, 2014). Physical evidence includes the environment (furniture, color, layout, noise level), supporting goods, space, sanitation and equipment, supporting facilities such as toilets, storage areas, yards. parking (Kukanja et al., 2016).

Successful marketers are those who maintain not only corporate profits but also consumer interests and loyalty through the firm's mix marketing decisions (Lamberti and Noci, 2010).

Attitude is an individual's positive or negative feelings about performing a certain behavior. Attitude describes the degree to which an individual views the outcome of an action as positive or negative (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1991).

Intention is the plan or possibility that someone will perform a particular action in a given context. Intention is a cognitive representation of a willingness to perform an action. The intention to act is the main driver of the behavior (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1991).

Purchase intention is described as a potential customer's willingness to purchase a product (Elbeck, 2008). The sales of the business can be surveyed based on the purchase intention of the customer. Predicting purchase intention is the first step to predicting actual customer buying behavior (Howard and Sheth, 1967). In addition, based on a number of theories, purchase intention is considered the basis for predicting future demand (Fishbein

and Ajzen, 1991).

2.3. Research hypothesis

2.3.1. Attitude affects purchase intention

Attitude in the TRA and TPB models is confirmed to affect intention. Studies of behavior and behavioral intention have both documented this effect. In green marketing studies, attitude also plays an important role in influencing green purchase intention (Shama 2021). The author re-tests this relationship in the context of green marketing of the Vietnamese retail industry with the hypothesis:

H1: Consumers' attitudes towards green food positively influence their purchase intention

2.3.2. Green promotion affects consumer attitudes

Consistent communication and interaction with customers helps understand their changing consumption trends (Sarkar et al., 2019; Testa et al., 2011). Green promotion involves using different marketing tools to promote green products (Leonidou et al., 2011). It positively affects consumers' green attitudes including skepticism (Albayrak et al., 2013; Kordshouli et al., 2015). Word of mouth (Gleim et al., 2013) can be more effective in green promotions. Ecolabels have been identified as a leading advertising technique (Brecard, 2014) to promote green products. This will help meet the needs of consumers seeking information before making a purchase (Aday & Yener, 2014). Attitudes are shaped by beliefs in values. The media will provide information that creates trust in the product's value and so green promotion will influence attitudes. Therefore, the author hypothesizes:

H2: Green promotion positively affects consumers' attitude towards green food.

2.3.3. Green products

The key to success in marketing is the attributes and quality of the product (Glanz et Al., 2012). Product design and styling induce product perceptions and feelings in customers, which in turn contribute to customer attitudes toward product purchase. (Lee et Al., 2021). In order to attract consumers' attention and build positive attitudes, products must also be highly applicable, practical, and trendy (Zheng et Al., 2020). Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Green products positively affect consumers' attitudes towards green food.

2.3.4. Green place

Green retail stores contribute to creating trust in good products and services, thereby building a positive attitude of consumers towards buying green products (Ahi & Searcy, 2013). From that, the author hypothesized:

H4: Distribution channel positively affects consumers' attitude towards green food.

2.3.5. Green pricing

Green products are often considered expensive (Zhao & Zhong, 2015) and the higher price often becomes a barrier for consumers to buy green products, affecting actual buying behavior and attitudes. (Steg et al., 2014). Newton and Meyer (2013) also observed that higher prices create barriers to the development of green products and affect consumers' willingness to pay for green products. This barrier can be overcome by raising awareness about the benefits of green products (Muller & Ruffieux, 2011). Processed green products are considered to be more expensive, so domestic production should be promoted to be cost-effective. In Vietnam, with low per capita income, high prices of green products can negatively affect consumer attitudes. So the following hypothesis is put forward:

H5: Product price positively affects consumers' attitude towards green food.

2.3.6. People

The people involved in the customer service process play an important role in shaping consumers' attitudes about purchasing a product. Their appearance, conversational style, and attitude can influence buyers' perceptions of products and services (Hu et Al., 2020). Knowledge of products and service quality from employees will affect customers' purchasing attitudes (Xu et Al., 2020). Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: People have a positive influence on consumers' attitudes towards green food.

2.3.7. Process

The service process is concerned with the production and delivery of a service. It is found that service process design indirectly affects customer perception (Kushwaha et al., 2015). Zheng (2020) argues that shopping and transaction processes are important factors affecting consumers' attitudes. If consumers feel convenience and ease, they will have a more positive attitude towards purchasing. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7: Customer service process positively affects consumers' attitude towards green food.

2.3.8. Physical evidence

Direct shoppers often experience the atmosphere of the shopping environment where the decoration, furniture and architecture make the viewer more connected to the context (Zhang et al., 2020) and this atmosphere is easily stimulated. Product information becomes more accessible to customers (Xu et al., 2020). Furthermore, the customer experience is enhanced through various consumption scenarios, such as live product demonstrations as well as attractive, diverse product displays to foster enthusiasm and arouse interest and elicit consumer buying behavior (Hu et al., 2020). Physical evidence will help buyers with product information as well as purchase inspiration. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H8: Physical evidence is positively associated with customers' attitude toward green purchase.

2.4. Research models

3. Research method

On the basis of an overview of studies related to green marketing tools, attitudes towards green buying behavior and green purchase intention, the research team has inherited the scales for research. A qualitative research was done with the collection of information through in-depth interviews with 2 groups of employees (5 people each)

of modern chain stores selling green food and 3 customer groups (each group of 5 to 7 people) who often shop at modern retail chains in Hanoi that sell green food. The content of the in-depth interviews focused on discussing green marketing tools, attitudes towards green buying behavior and green buying intentions. The results of this research phase help to calibrate the scale and complete the set of questions for quantitative research. Here are the official scales stopped for quantitative research:

Factors	Variable code	Variable name
Green Products	prod1	Product diversity
	prod2	Adequate packaging
	prod3	Well-done packaging
Green Price	pric1	Cheaper Price
	pric2	Follow price development
	pric3	Negotiable Price
	pric4	Offering Discount
Green Distribution	dist1	Strategic location
	dist2	Delivery service
	dist3	Place identity
	dist4	Product availability
Green Media	prom1	Simple Bonus of Purchasing
	prom2	Mouth-of-Word Promotion
	prom3	Media Information (HP/Leaflet)
Human Factor	peop1	Manage business by itself
	peop2	Hospitable attitude
	peop3	Alacrity/Agile/ Quick Response
	peop4	Honesty
Service Procedure	proc1	Bargaining in kinship
	proc2	Payment flexibility
Physical environment	evid1	Market cleanliness
	evid2	Neatly arranged
	evid3	Shopping Flexibility/Convenience
Green food purchasing intention	inte1	I will actively buy green food
	inte2	I will definitely buy green food
	inte3	I will buy green food next time
	inte4	Likely I will buy green food if it is available in my area
	inte5	In the future, I will try green food if I need a product like that
Attitude toward green food	atti1	Purchasing green food is enjoyable
	atti2	I like purchasing green food
	atti3	Purchasing green food is interesting
	atti4	Purchasing green food is not frustrating discipline
	atti5	I get a lot of satisfaction purchasing green food
	atti6	I'm not afraid of purchasing green food

The quantitative research phase is conducted by collecting information by sending questionnaire links directly to customers through the Zalo network. From the customer database of modern stores, a list of 1000 customers

(including 350 people in Hanoi, 300 people in Da Nang and 350 people in Ho Chi Minh City) are randomly selected for the link. As a result, more than 400 customers responded. The data collected after removing biased and incomplete responses left 368 valid observations. According to Hair et al (1998), the minimum sample size suitable for factor analysis is determined by the formula $n=5*m$ (where m is the number of observed variables). To conduct regression analysis in the best way (Tabachnick et al., 2012), the sample size must ensure the formula: $n \geq 8m + 50$ (n is sample size, m is the number of independent variables in the model.); while according to (Harris, 2001): $n \geq 104 + m$ (where m is the number of independent and dependent variables, or $n \geq 50 + m$, if $m < 5$). The study has a total of 35 variables with 24 variables. independent, therefore, the sample size with 368 observations is large enough to perform statistical analysis. Data was coded and processed by SPSS software and Amos version 26.

4. Result

4.1. The results of testing the reliability of the scale

No	Factors	Number of observed variables	Cronbach's Alpha coefficient	Total variable correlation coefficient (within range)
1	Green product element	4	0,923	0,821-0,888
2	Green price factor	4	0,932	0,749-0,893
3	Green distribution element	4	0,91	0,727-0,826
4	Green media element	3	0,893	0,763-0,814
5	Human factors	4	0,821	0,616-0,647
6	Service process element	2	0,879	0,785-0,785
7	Physical environmental factors	3	0,919	0,837-0,845
8	Attitude factor	6	0,904	0,613-0,824
9	Green purchase intention factor	5	0,90	0,70-0,817

Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and total variable correlation coefficient are used to analyze the reliability of the scale. According to Peterson (1994), the value levels of Cronbach's Alpha have the following significance: a value greater than 0.8 indicates a good scale; between 0.7 and 0.8 the scale can be used; from 0.6 or more, the scale can be used in case the research concept or research context is new. According to Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), observed variables with a total correlation coefficient less than 0.3 will need to be removed. According to the results of data processing, the factors in the model all have Cronbach's Alpha coefficients greater than 0.8, the correlation coefficients of all variables are greater than 0.61. Thus, all the scales of the factors in the model meet the testing standards and can confirm enough reliability to perform the next analysis.

4.2. Exploratory factor analysis results

According to Hair & ctg (1998), the conditions for exploratory factor analysis must meet the following requirements (1) The KMO number shelf ranges from 0.5 to 1; (2) Factor loading > 0.5 ; (3) Bartlett's test has statistical significance (Sig. < 0.05); (4) Percentage of variance $> 50\%$. Data processing results for coefficient KMO=0.888; Bartlett's test has Sig ~ 0 , the total variance extracted is 70.522% and the factor loading coefficients of the variables are as follows:

	Factor								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
atti6	.913								
atti2	.886								
atti3	.824								
atti1	.756								
atti4	.705								
atti5	.548								
inte4		.892							
inte5		.866							
inte2		.834							
inte1		.685							
inte3		.683							
pric4			.947						
pric2			.912						
pric1			.910						
pric3			.717						
dist2				.916					
dist4				.877					
dist3				.869					
dist1				.681					
evid3					.907				
evid1					.889				
evid2					.873				
peop1						.743			
peop2						.742			
peop3						.737			
peop4						.664			
prod2							.937		
prod1							.870		
prod3							.848		
prom2								.897	
prom3								.893	
prom1								.779	
proc2									.887
proc1									.883

Thus, the exploratory factor analysis results ensure the testing standards. All observed variables have factor loading coefficients greater than 0.5 and converge on the correct factors as the theoretical model. Analysis results factors confirmed.

4.3. Analysis results of SEM linear structural model

According to Hu & Bentler (1999), the linear structural analysis model is considered suitable if the following test criteria are met:

- Chi-Square/df (CMIN/df): If CMIN/df 3 is good, if <5 is acceptable;

- Comparative fit index (CFI): if CFI 0.95 is very good, ≥ 0.9 is good, ≥ 0.8 is acceptable;
- Tucker–Lewis index (TLI): if TLI 0.95 is very good, ≥ 0.9 is good, ≥ 0.8 is acceptable;
- Goodness of fit index (GFI): if GFI 0.95 is very good, ≥ 0.9 is good,
- Root mean square errors of approximation (RMSEA): if RMSEA 0.06 is good, 0.08 is acceptable.

The P-values in the results of the analysis of the linear structural model represent the statistical significance level to accept or reject the research hypothesis (usually studies use the significance level Alpha=0.05).

Results of linear structural model analysis on the impact of green marketing tools on attitude towards green food purchase behavior and green food purchase intention.

The research model includes the impact relationship between value assets, brand equity, and relationship assets on the intention to repeat consumption. The results after analyzing and making some adjustments show that the research model is compatible with the experimental data with Chi-square indexes = 1.625 (less than 2), CFI = 0.964, TLI = 0.960, GFI = 0.889 are all greater than 0.85; RMSEA = 0.041 is less than 0.08. Thus, the linear structural model ensures the testing standards and is consistent with the market data. The normalized linear structure model is as follows:

All P_value < 0.05 of the regression coefficients are less than 0.05 and the regression coefficients all have positive values, showing a positive impact on the outcome variable:

The effect	Regression weight	Conclusion
att ←--- pric	.123	Hypothesis H5 (price has a positive effect on green food buying attitude) is confirmed

atti	<---	dist	.325	The hypothesis H4 (distribution channel has a positive influence on green food purchase attitude) is confirmed
atti	<---	evid	.088	The hypothesis H8 (physical environment positively affects the attitude to buy green food) is confirmed
atti	<---	peop	.144	The hypothesis H6 (human factors positively affect the attitude to buy green food) is confirmed
atti	<---	prod	.133	Hypothesis H3 (product positively affects green food purchase attitude) is confirmed
atti	<---	pro m	.215	The hypothesis H2 (communication positively affects the attitude to buy green food) is confirmed
atti	<---	proc	.088	Hypothesis H7 (service process positively affects green food purchase attitude) is confirmed
int e	<---	atti	.406	Hypothesis H1 (attitude positively affects intention to buy green food) is confirmed

5. Discussion and implication

The research results confirm that attitude towards green food positively affects customers' intention to buy it. Out of a normalized regression of 0.406, it shows that if the attitude towards green food increases by 1 unit, the intention to buy increases by 0.406 units. To promote green food purchase intention of customers, it is necessary to promote positive customer attitude towards it. Green marketing tools affect its purchase intention through mediating attitude towards green food.

Research results also show that green marketing tools have a positive effect on attitudes towards green food. This shows that marketing activities will change attitudes towards green food and thus affect consumers' intention to buy it.

The marketing tool that has the strongest influence on attitude towards green food and its purchase intention is the driving factor. This shows that giving customers convenient access to green food will have a strong impact on customer's attitude or in other words, the direct contact of customers with it will affect the customer's attitude towards green food and strongly influence the positive attitude of customers and thereby affect the intention to buy it. Therefore, modern retail stores should pay attention to ensuring the availability of green food, choosing the location and delivery method to create the most favorable conditions for customers to access it.

Communication is the second strongest factor influencing attitudes towards green food. This once again affirms the very important role of communication in changing customers' attitudes and intentions to buy green food. Therefore, businesses need to invest in communication activities at the point of sale to promote positive attitudes towards green food and thereby influence green purchase intentions.

Product, price and people equally influence attitudes towards green food. This shows that marketers need to factor in *product, price and people* at the point of sale to contribute to creating a positive attitude towards green food and thereby influence customers' green food buying behavior.

Physical evidence and *service process* have the least influence on attitude towards green food and its purchase intention. Therefore, modern retail stores do not need to focus on the service process and physical environment at the point of sale in order to promote consumers' green buying attitudes and behavior.

6. Conclusion

The study has shown the positive impact of marketing tools on customers' intention to buy green food at modern retail stores through the mediating variable of attitude towards it. The research results also show the direction for investing in marketing activities to promote green buying behavior of customers. This study only focuses on marketing activities at the point of sale without taking into account the impact of green food manufacturers' marketing activities on customers' intention to buy it. Further studies should examine the simultaneous influence of marketing activities at retail food stores and marketing and branding activities of green food manufacturers on customers' purchase intention of green food.

Acknowledgement: The Ministry of Education and Training supported this work, Viet Nam [grant number B2021.KHA.05].

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